

Participants			
Participant	Are you currently working with Micro Frontends?	How much professional experience do you have with Micro Frontends?	What type of role do you play or have you played when working with Micro Frontends?
P1	No	More than 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P2	No	Between 1 and 2 years	Software Architect
P3	Yes	More than 2 years	Software Architect
P4	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P5	Yes	More than 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P6	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P7	No	More than 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P8	Yes	More than 2 years	Software engineering team leader
P9	No	Between 1 and 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P10	Yes	More than 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P11	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P12	Yes	More than 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P13	Yes	Less than 1 year	Fullstack Developer
P14	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P15	Yes	More than 2 years	Mobile
P16	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P17	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer
P18	Yes	Between 1 and 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P19	No	Between 1 and 2 years	Fullstack Developer
P20	Yes	More than 2 years	Frontend developer